

Development through Other Eyes in the Era of Globalization: Taking the Discussion Forward

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ABSTRACT: This paper, part literature review and part critique, examines neoliberalism with its triumphalist view of development, which has not changed; it remains rooted in an oppressive colonial narrative and “dialogue,” designed to disrupt economic rights and self-determination, reproduce hegemonic identities and discountenance that anything can be learned from the “Other.” Furthermore, it claimed “new” thinking to “authentic” dialogue is neither new nor equitable, its hostility to indigeneity and that defines what it means to be fully human, and the underlying injustices meet the needs of colonialism as they bottleneck reciprocity. The idea of radically changing its content with frameworks centered on assimilation, and the destruction of traditional knowledge and cultures that are incapable of reproducing “colonial post” is imperative. The paper argues that privileging ethics and reparative justice for all decenters enslavement of the mind, restores decolonized thinking that denaturalizes rendering the “Other” as a passive and docile visitor in imperialist development and creates diverse spaces for people to liberate themselves from global apartheid capitalism. Development was never really on the civilization agenda in the first place, thus the need to dismantle the hegemony of coloniality remains completely blocked from re-inscribing the right to development.

Keywords: Development; Coloniality; Aid Generosity; Human Rights; Decolonization; Reciprocity; Neoliberalism.

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“The most potent weapon in the hands of the oppressor is the mind of the oppressed.” —Steve Biko

“The problem is not so much that development has failed as that it was never really on the agenda in the first place. By all indications political conditions in Africa are the greatest impediment to development” (Ake, 1996: 1).

1. Introduction

Developmental recreation, decolonial thinking, and horizontal dialogue affirm political freedom from oppression—mandated by the 1993 Vienna Declaration and Program of Action (VDPA), which addresses the historical harms of colonization. In a de-colonial context, the VDPA is not a treatise on universal truth, but an act of sabotage. It reaffirms that all people are inherently worthy and promised human rights and freedoms (Lewis 2011) and reestablishes the 1986 UN Declaration on the Right to Development (see Articles 1, 3, and 4; Schrijver 2020). These two Declarations view the right to development as a comprehensive economic, social, cultural, and political process. They solidify the interdependence between these factors and the right to liberation and declare that self-determination is impossible under colonization. It is not only incompatible with local cultures, as it is akin to the coloniality of power, which requires a “decolonial turn” from Eurocentric forms of imagining and seeing and knowing the world within which we exist (Andreotti 2006; Baker 2012; Mignolo 2011). Indeed, this which has changed ‘our’ world—only celebrates positivity, forced assimilation, and unequal integration, undermining our human rights, and sustaining the destruction of our cultures. Meaningful change, toward liberation—forces us to take another look at the challenges of economic, social, and cultural effects of coloniality on First World natives

Article 12 of the 1986 UN Declaration illustrates other principal challenges for achieving social and reparative justice. We cannot stress how crucial these challenges are for humanity: the untidy affirmation that no phraseology can substitute for reality; taking

advantage of development aid opportunities; and facing the threat of societies transforming into nation-states. Decolonization or decoloniality has irreversibly poisoned values by tirelessly punctuating its dismantling of world order, with the destruction of Indigenous culture and education customs. According to Frank Fanon, this encounter between two congenitally antagonistic forces demolishes and naturalizes power and practice. These both decenter the enslavement of the mind and dislocate the Other, ensure reciprocity privilege ethics and principles of reparative justice for all, and connect people to their local reality. through cultural rediscovery and self-reconstruction that is at the heart of non-scientific knowledge and non-homogenous and complex ways of education. (Baker, 2012; Maldonado-Torres, 2016; Mignolo, 2009; Odora Hoppers 2002). By reducing injustices in the production of knowledge, and by unlearning alien knowledge, decolonization reconstructs education, enabling people to function in their complex and connected world.

By providing a sense of indigeneity, reconstructed education necessitates agency of sovereignty and control over development and natural resources. Not only does it mitigate colonialist dialogue and mentalities, but it also abates structural problems that privilege capitalist exploitation. Accordingly, minimizing the influence of what Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2013:37) refers to as “the snare of colonial matrices of power”, which bluntly stated, these colonialist and capitalist elements undermine creating spaces where being is practiced as freedom—where people liberate themselves from the colonial world: a world that denies inalienable rights. This modern brand of colonialism differs from that of the ‘colonizers.’ wherein competing imperial nations established colonies in the ‘New World’ to dominate and battle with each other to exploit “pieces” of local wealth,

The right to development as self-determination—which was denied both then and now—can be realized by fostering a love for wisdom, and by recognizing 1) the extraordinary productiveness of First World natives, and 2) the capacity of decentering to guide development and ward against the corrosive,. Such recognition speeds up decolonization affirming the right to self-development. Decolonization by removing exploiters’ brutality and oppressors’ heterogeneity supports Africanization on the grounds of sovereignty, as the state represents a diversity of social transformations rather than the hegemony of power. The insularity of histories and historiographical traditions favors anticolonial thinking, which entails living together in a differentiated space and keeping hope alive for self-determination.

This article draws from several UN Declarations, affirming that the struggle for self-determination is consistent with freedom as an individual and collective right to development, as will be discussed in the following sections. Accordingly, this concept of self-determination goes beyond the mainstream model of development, which has gaps and limitations in its normative contents. In our view, development is a comprehensive process centered on participation and self-determination, by which beneficiaries have the freedom to enjoy their desired economic, social, cultural, and political developments. The obligation to safeguard these substantive rights rests on the shoulders of all stakeholders, particularly international executors of development to establish decolonization policies that contend with the material world of darkness. In decoloniality, First World natives can no longer be viewed as a deforming element in need of values and insensible to ethics.

This paper, which is necessarily selective and incomplete, explores the development's underside (coloniality) and provides a decolonial understanding that allows for alternative knowledge and thinking situated in the exteriority of the Global North hegemony. The paper then highlights 'the basic and universal social impact of 'historical power asymmetries produced coloniality of power' narrative of 'hegemonic' neoliberal coloniality, as characterized by its 'absolute truth' imposed on the whole people, its narcissistic dialogue, and its corrosive elements. To develop the argument, the paper is divided into 4 sections: the first section explains what is coloniality; Section two, shows how coloniality of knowledge is pushing to adopt reforms knowledge system; the third section, calls for rethinking coloniality to mitigate the clutches of dominating power relationship which has brought distortions in local knowledge systems; final section presents what is required for dismantling coloniality that denies multiplicity of knowledge systems. The paper concludes by asserting in differentiated realities, the colonial matrix of power is propounded to legitimize oppressive imposition and dominating relationships, and we must ensure space for self-recreation.

The inhumane brutality of the Global Northern-driven modernization project of colonialism—traced back through five hundred years of imperialism, and in its modern form of coloniality—removes the Other from its heterogeneity by unifying itself on an international basis as the uncivilized visitor via global capitalism (Said 1980; Rahnema and Bawtree 1997). For example, by dislocating the Other from self-conceptualization, the Global North claims the most advanced qualities of human civilizations, as distinguished from 'barbaric' native cultures, which are thus disqualified from participation.

Likewise, certain knowledge systems were considered appropriate for expressing intelligence, while other knowledge systems were considered inferior. Only when we recognize the need to promote 'inclusion' and 'equity,' which entail the practice of non-discriminatory pedagogy, and sensitivity to various dimensions of inequality between insiders and outsiders, can the Other be brought into the fullness of humanness. Such a realignment of interests reinforces new development; from that new development, new rights, and a shift from an imperialistic approach to a "global agency" approach (a more common agenda from which all nations benefit through the collective subscription to that agenda and its pursuit. With this recognition comes a redesign of learning and development aid around the pluriversality of knowledge and corresponding diverse ways of being in the world. Within our logic is an understanding that the coloniality of knowledge systems is inherently complex and unsustainable and resists the struggle for creative power and mutual humanization found in globalization.

The above thinking undermines domesticating reality; the power of oppression can only suggest that such thinking "contests knowledge singularity modernity" through the establishment of new realities. It reticulates the recreation of self-driven modernity and the political possibilities associated with changing entrenched colonialism; it contests conventional mainstream narratives. On all different fronts, exploitative forces used deculturization, imaginative disfigurement, and brutality to naturalize power and remap human spaces, accompanied by and situated within international inequalities. This is the big picture of the current neoliberal project of global capitalism, which Mignolo(2001) argued:

Colonial legacies are still alive and well as central strategies of subalternization. Subalternity,... was not only economic but intellectual as well, as far as a concept of humanity linked to intelligence first and the concept of reason later were attributed to certain groups of people and denied to others. In parallel form, certain languages were considered appropriate to express certain levels of intelligence or reason, and other languages were considered inferior to the people who spoke to them. (Mignolo, 2001b, p. 178)

Colonialism comes with great power, which in turn comes with irresponsibility, which we define here as a deprivation of the right to development under globalization, which dismantles traditional systems, reorganizing mindsets to impose on the Other its global corporate culture. Globalization underscores the hegemonic project of this reduction of epistemic diversity, and the resulting strategic control of self-creation, favoring multinational and transnational corporations' suppression of alternative desired development. This legacy of colonialism, which survives within the domains of knowledge and the undermining of agency of development rights, led the United Nations Resolution 3201 (S-VI), to establish the 1974 New International Economic Order (NIEO), which declares the sovereign equality of States, the self-determination of all peoples, the inadmissibility of the acquisition of territories by force, territorial integrity, and noninterference in the internal affairs of other States.

In the authors' opinion, globalization's strategic control of knowledge through the varied dimensions of decolonization has become disconnected from the right to development and its associated struggles against colonialism (Mbembe 2014, Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2012; 2013; Mamdani 2013; Mignolo 2007). This division between the interrogation of power and the right to development—which stemmed from the discontentment that independence movements developed during their struggle for political liberation—did not regenerate Indigenous knowledge. Nor did their projects translate into overturning colonial structures. Instead, this disconnect has resulted in denied democratic accountability and a loss of economic equality and social justice.

In short, this failure to redress existing social injustices, accompanied by educational standardization, together objectifies new ways of knowing, seeing, and being in the denied world. The terms “decolonial thinking/decolonization” may be used in other senses in other literature, but for our article, they comprise the human obligation to implement reparative global justice and to question the legitimacy of colonization. Decolonial thinking seeks legitimacy in local contexts. We argue that the right to development is a struggle to subvert and decenter power through the centrality of people's realities. Developmental voices replace the alien voices, spaces, and worldviews of globalization's knowledge reproduction. Moreover, within decoloniality, Others' interests directly challenge colonial inaction toward societies plagued by ills created through colonization and linguistic genocide. Coloniality traces directly to conflicting agendas and flawed policies that keep First World natives from creating self-awareness as participants in the global village.

Border Thinking and Vulnerability as a Knowing Otherwise

Decolonial thinking plays a key role in the critical endeavor of modernity (Icaza 2010; 2015; Taylor 2012; Icaza and Vazquez 2013) affirms as it acknowledges that there is ‘no modernity without coloniality’ (Quijano 2000; Mignolo 2003; 2013; Walsh 2007; 2010; 2011; 2012; Lugonés 2010a; 2010b; Vazquez 2009; 2011; 2014). The relevance of this affirmation is that coloniality as the underside of modernity constitutes an epistemic location from which all realities are thought. In pursuit of border thinking, even decoloniality in their agendas, international laws and power dynamics have favored Northern ‘modernity’ and the irreversible, evolutionary process leading to the domination of the most powerful. These are the damaging effects of neoliberalism and its legacy: depriving nation-states of their sovereignty and citizens of their economic rights, reinforcing contemporary imperialism, and compromising native capacities. It hollows out development opportunities for First World natives. These destructive practices—which mitigate the right to developmental processes that put people at the center of development, to recover latent knowledge and repressed development—are afforded greater currency in this paper. In many ways, imperialist control, which is not as explicit and obvious as colonial control, enforces the exploitation of indigenous resources by failing to serve the best interests of First World natives, leading to a revamped form of colonialism.

Neoliberalism’s cultural logic, or World Bank/IMF opaque reforms and “getting institutions right” policy, linked to its Structural Adjustment Program, achieves its aims by ignoring ethics and realities, and replacing traditional value systems with invisible power structures and cultural genocide, perpetuating colonialism. In contrast to the Bank’s claim to empower countries grappling with development challenges, facilitate knowledge for development, and catalyze building capacity, this article illustrates that its hidden face is an intersection of epistemic and political global coloniality. With the survival of coloniality following the end of direct colonial capitalism, nothing has changed for First World natives. The ‘one-size-fits-all’ idea of development organized for the Global South by the Global North and the World Bank has become associated with underdevelopment, insensitivity to human rights and needs, imposing aligned values, castigating fugitive knowledge, fostering inequality of opportunities and liberties, and serving as gatekeepers, regulating the production of knowledge in the First World native’s world (Mamdani 2020; Ngũgĩ 1986). This has led to increasing doubt about the role of the international community in promoting development and global social justice. Thus, ‘development’ continues to mean battling against walls of power and struggling against underdevelopment.

A broad range of studies, including those by the World Bank (2005a) and UNCTAD (2006), provide evidence that cultural logic and initiated reforms by the international community are at the heart of developmental problems; they also show that the international community cannot address or redress the unjust distribution of power, which militates against providing room for a more diverse understanding of the social and cultural dimensions of development. As such, neoliberalism, which lacks appreciation for local conditions and sensitivities, leads to unequal relations for dependence and yields societal stasis, as developmental beneficiaries are not participants in its processes. Indeed, to

unlock social transformation is to give sufficient policy space and sensitivity to indigeneness in development.

The work of William Easterly (2006), Claude Ake (1996), and Geo-JaJa and Zajda (2005), reinforces the idea that First World nations' well-being and complex problems were not high priorities for the international community, which had found room to grow inside them. In many cases, the international community was reluctant to heed natives' ideas of mutuality and sovereignty; such calls went against the favor of the larger community. Instead, they committed to controlling First World natives by inoculating them into a "Culture of Silence." Steve Biko highlighted another way of looking at this colonization of the mind. He asserts that domination and repression were the most potent weapons in the hands of the oppressor, as they captured the minds of the oppressed, disconnecting them from their roots, and disrupting paths toward the establishment of anti-colonial societies and eventual freedom. He further asserted that this imposition was the most profound impact of colonialism on natives' lives.

This colonization of the mind is not pivotal for development; nor is it a remedy for complexities resulting from limiting possibilities and encouraging a state of marginality. Rather, this mental colonization can only complicate ideas of reciprocity, relationality, culture, and ethics, which are enormously influential in establishing freedom. There is little doubt that coupling aid and its divisive Cold War policies, including cultural imposition, is unlikely to deliver the development needed for the world. The World Bank notes that even with the inflow of aid, income inequality and poverty have increased globally, despite development aid making a difference in people's lives (World Bank, 2002). It is precisely here that we can draw useful lessons for a 'new' version of anti-colonial policy. We suggest that the solution is to dismantle the fugitive status of Indigenous knowledge, preventing the loss of native knowledge via a new relational knowledge-making framework.

This paper explores the right to development, and the recognition on the part of the donor that aid manipulated and deployed by the Global North perpetuates harmful development patterns, as it is rooted in colonialism. The Global South has called out to be listened to in a way that both honors their epistemologies and envisions development as sharing rights and responsibilities in a partnership founded on a mutual understanding of each other's goals and strategies. To this end, development partnerships should not be condescending or limited to pathways that produce unequal relations, as colonialism did. Accordingly, while no nation liberates herself by her efforts alone, neither is she liberated by others. This paper arises from the just and normative assertion that development is a human right. Our contribution to this topic is that in its absence of liberation decoloniality, for an entire range of reasons, the neoliberal hegemonic practice of 'development' hobbles the Global South. Its agenda denies the historical roots of the universality of epistemology, aims to deliver fixed bodies of knowledge, and is insensitive to the recipient's identity. As such, the Global South calls out for rethinking development to help it reclaim its right to development that colonialism stripped away.

This article focuses on the recognition of the right to development and features four main sections, apart from the introduction. The following section traces the evolution of education and its key role in shaping cultures and societies. Developmental education

controversy stems from foreign knowledge systems intentionally designed to produce First World natives who end up with foreign values. This turns schools into battlegrounds for the soul of the locals and tools for reengineering society. The next section elucidates the relevant normative contents of neoliberalism, locating its gaps and limitations, to highlight alternative development paths. We explore United Nations Declarations to provide points of departure from the progressive realization of all human rights in neoliberal development. Instead, development must be conducted by human rights standards. The fourth section begins with an analysis of the neoliberal entrapment of culture and its covert objective of stealing reflection, recreation, and action to transform the world. We comment on globalization's added value for the realization of the right to development. The concluding section summarizes our takeaways, which led us to rethink coloniality in line with anti-colonial thinking and reconstruct neoliberal development discourse to truly embody respect for the Other according to human rights standards. We propose a decolonial reality-driven aid, or a world of equality in a restructured international power order, allowing the South to participate in their own socioeconomic matters.

2. Reality of Education in Neoliberalism

The sobering reality is that the significant inflow of development assistance—particularly structural adjustment loans—provided over the past 40 years are neither economically feasible nor politically acceptable, as these approaches to development ignore substantive rights to development and education. Not only do educational rights activate ontological and epistemological politics that attach intrinsic value to life, realigning education with the overall aim of sustaining life on Earth, but by defining schooling upward, educational rights create curricula that determine what constitutes knowledge, and places learning at the heart of decoloniality (see Uvin 2007; Wu and Geo-JaJa 2016). This is why aid practices and Bretton Wood Institutions loan terms unadjusted for First World natives and their economies—current and future—leave developing nation-states suffering under considerable privations and longing for a return to colonization, leaving countries immersed in the 'darker side' of globalization. Moreover, globalization/coloniality insidiously features capitalist expansion and the perpetuation of domination. Globalization aims to subsume “the Other under the Same,” a deculturization project achieved through the imposition of hegemonic practices. In *Development as Poison*, Marglin lays out the consequences of this erroneous worldview, asserting that:

The citizen of a developing nation — the “other” — is thus seen as “a miniature adult, and development means the tender nurturing by the market to form the miniature Indian or African into a full-size American.” The second view places great emphasis on cultural dissimilarities and sees the “other” cultures as needing “structural transformation and cultural improvement” to take on the “adult” qualities of the industrialized nations (Marglin 2003:71).

According to Andreotti (2010: 8-9), this perspective creates impoverished communities, wherein inhabitants attempt to improve their lives through development aid,

perpetuating the inconsequentiality of human development and structural transformation. Why has the global community not administered such aid to Africa as that given to Europe through the Marshall Plan following World War II?

Education is a central asset for developing knowledge, but as developmental education was not designed for First World natives' needs, it has instead yielded the darkness of underdevelopment that development intended to overcome. It disavowed 'indigeneity' and 'oppression' as alien curricula and genocidal language, making such claims meaningless in local contexts; in many ways, developmental education has emptied native minds. These issues suggest disingenuousness in the curriculum. The authors observe that current 'schooling practices,' in particular curricula that are front/center or redefine the learning agenda, while pedagogical, undermine critical insights into the progressive goals of education. Globalization's increasing subordination and commodification of education is fundamentally wrong, in not giving voice to native canons of knowledge. Corporate agendas in education, and their explicit linkage to educational practices and agendas, support the neoliberal civilizational project and economic apartheid. This transfer of educational power away from local governments is hostile to both political equality and equal opportunities. These are a result of colonialism.

By not interrogating the outcomes of colonialism and capitalism, alien education results in epistemological blindness, silencing other cultures and knowledge. When educational content matters—particularly when globalization continues to dominate demand for specific knowledge and skills—educational decolonization matters even more, as local needs are central; education will not decenter other knowledge systems in a global context. This reasoning offers a seductive but deceptive type of education that turns learners into consumers of the colonizers' culture. As a result, de-culturalization liquidates the cultural background of locals, galvanizing them into contributing to the social transformation of their locality, as they are made subhuman, leading to the cultural alienation of their population. Modern de-culturalization, just like coloniality, is another proof that constructive development was never on the agenda; the destruction of the colonial world would be the abolition of this artificial bifurcation of humanity. Such liberation threatens the presumed universality and superiority of alien culture, conditioned via the vestiges of the colonial footprint in the Global South.

Today, education is still firmly rooted in a "colonial and assimilationist logic that deculturizes Africans . . . as it is now politicized and commodified to meet the demand of globalization (Geo-JaJa and Zajda 2005). Moreover, national educational policies and practices no longer foster a life that is culturally enriching and morally and ethically justifiable. Such education invalidates the space and time needed to develop situated learning, as it discourages the practice of freedom, or people participating in the transformation of their world. Following independence, First World natives retained colonial languages, maintained colonial curricula, and relied on books featuring veiled disparagement of Indigenous cultures, thus delinking them from their local realities (Babaci-Wilhite et al 2012). These educational ruptures require rethinking the civilization project and outside neoliberalism and delinking from globalization's capitalist economy. As globalization has not met its promises of education for a better future, it is time to rethink that education.

Andreotti (2011) argues that dismantling cultural imperialism's hegemonic schooling is a process of learning to read the world through Others' eyes, invoking ideas of rights in education. Similarly, Frantz Fanon, who struggled for the liberation and decolonizing of Africa, and the recreation of First World natives, described the deep-seated malaise of living under the bondage of globalization. Reflecting on the imperial notion of the Other and economic approaches to collective responsibility,, Fanon notes that:

Colonialism is not satisfied merely with holding a people in its grip and emptying the native's brain of all form and content. By a kind of perverse logic, it turns to the past of the oppressed people, and distorts it, disfigures and destroys it. "This work of devaluing pre-colonial history takes on a dialectical significance today." -Franz Fanon, *The Wretched...*1961 (as quoted in Walter Mignolo's *Delinking*)

The motivations of colonialism, and the falsehood of its generosity, as captured in the above quotation, show that not only has education become more a part of the problem than the solution, but countries have also become increasingly dependent and internationalized; they have withdrawn from providing education to equip their learners to create a world beyond oppressive relationships. Such education, which inserts nation-states into the capitalist system, produces learners who are servants of globalization and thus rendered a 'waste.' Walter Mignolo asserts that First World natives who seek to challenge unquestionable 'truth' and inscrutable value for their self-recreation, must first understand coloniality if they are to dismantle constituted structures and bring about change. Externally imposed worldviews and walls of disparity created by the interpreters of development empty the native's brain of all content, instead of reducing subordination and eliminating hegemony. This quest for relevance, and the accompanying narrative of discouragement against listening and learning from the Other, only mitigate the gains of globalization.

Nobel Prize-winning economist Joseph Stiglitz has argued: that no longer is schooling in the Global South a tool to prepare people for life in their local society, or for the life they desire, or to address inequalities in their development (see Freire 1970); it is no longer even the driver of development, or development itself, as argued by Paulo Freire in *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (1970). We argue that recolonization of the mind decenters freeing the human mind and the creative thought processes required to imagine new worlds. To address these educational limitations at the heart of underdevelopment, we need to decolonize epistemologies that connect people to their roots, and that privilege relational equality and sharing, to denaturalize feeling inferior. According to Freire, by increasingly subordinating education to the logic of neoliberal capitalism, ethics, culture, and equity become tools of domestication, cultural repression, and the denial of human dignity. This blueprint for controlling nation-states' educational authority crystallizes neoliberal educational policies.

In the paper, "Five Debates on International Development: The U. S Perspective," a former Director of USAID argued that the principal reason for decreasing foreign aid was the absence of clearly understood security threats to the strategic interests of major donors

which developmental assistance could remedy (Natsios, 2006: 132). In contrast, President John F. Kennedy, who created USAID, states that its mission is “to prevent the social injustice and economic chaos upon which subversion and revolt feed.” Under this assertion, neoliberalism is a dead strategy, as it lends itself too easily to the “agenda and practice of oppression”: imperialism and underdevelopment in the mind and heart of the recipient. Neoliberal oversimplification erodes human rights and ethics, weakening trust in developmental cooperation. What we do argue, therefore, is that ethics, ‘trust,’ and human rights in every sphere can restore the right to development. The other important substantive element of the right to development is that it guarantees an equitable share in the fruits of development, such as economic, social, cultural, civil, and political rights. By producing equality of opportunity and creating diverse development paths, the right to development embodies substantive elements of ethics and “do no harm” in the civilization project. The right to development lies at the heart of developmental problems. It redresses colonial practices and unjust distributions of power that impede dismantling coloniality.

Under the failed iteration of modern development, the Global South has become even more pulverized, underdeveloped, and fragile, due to the suppression of critical thinking and the disempowering nature of donors’ mission to ‘civilize’ First World ‘natives.’ These are grave matters, questioning the donor country’s conviction of its superiority as the storehouse of knowledge and liberator of the oppressed. Colonialism asserts that the North has wisdom, and the South has a culture; the North has science, and First World natives have lives and ways of life that do not matter. Unfortunately, the imperial interpretation of the South as uncivilized is still alive and well. But new constructs of humanity—that the glories of the North should have come to an end—call for education to begin unlearning, among other things, this assumption.

Saturated with this idea of Northern supremacy, ‘aid,’ which primarily represents destruction and plunder, is the impetus of globalization’s inevitable underdevelopment. This is why the practice of capitalism/coloniality, its scope not limited to Africa, engenders in recipients of aid practices of freedom that do not liberate, the accurate feeling that knowledge is controlled to their disadvantage and that the ‘development’ of people and capital across borders allows for ‘differences’ between globalizing projects. This project, which serves to elevate the North, only pressures countries in the Global South to attain the status of Global Northern “modernity” over understanding that the North’s global presence is due to inventions from a particular geohistorical context: in which the North educated First World natives how to understand themselves and the world. Naturally, this uncritical, colonial transfer of knowledge from one reality to another serves to exclude the Other from participating in the transformation of their own world: fighting to destroy those causes that nourish false charity, and learning to contribute as equal human beings to the machinations of global development (see Paulo Freire, *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Chapter 2).

As things presently stand, Geo-JaJa & Majhanovich (2017) note that aid comes with the imperative that recipients conform to impositions that merely reproduce unequal relations between them, as in the previous colonialist era. We remind the reader that the practice of freedom is vital to any humanistic approach to education for development. However, as seen in this article, restorative justice and truthful education forcefully

challenge dominant views of development, from a range of normative elements associated with rights, freedom, ethics, and equity. We cannot even begin to tackle dimensions of cultural or developmental imperialism without taking a closer look at alienating educational systems, seeking reforms inconsistent with the universal abstract, and taking a concrete step into a world unknown. The unknown world derives from educational rights that promote a new developmental framework, borrowing from abroad as necessary, but developed locally, within an autonomous system capable of generating reciprocity.

3. Normative Development Repackaged As Cultural Supremacy

This section elucidates the normative contents of development, and highlights neoliberalism's gaps and limitations, providing a point of departure for the subsequent analysis of the right to development. In this paper, decolonization and decoloniality are exchangeable in context. However, the reader must keep in mind the distinctions between political decolonization and liberation decolonization. The former is the struggle to undo the establishment of an unequal political system for indigenous peoples, while the other is centered on ethics, and rapid socioeconomic transformation through struggling against 'development unfreedom' and uncovering the histories of those whom Frantz Fanon refers to as the "wretched of the Earth." "Winds of change" in the colonies offer access to new social standings and political rights.

Fanon asserts that colonialism is not satisfied with oppressing people and emptying their brains of form and content. Instead, colonialism degrades First World natives to an inferior status, and attacks their cultural places, recolonizing them (Fanon 2001). As with Mignolo's celebrated work, *Coloniality of Power and De-Colonial Thinking* (2007), and Thiong'o's *Decolonizing the Mind* (1986), Fanon critiques coloniality for its cultural destruction, devaluation of history, and linguistic genocide. Thiong'o argues that the greatest weapon unleashed by imperialism was the 'Cultural Bomb': the annihilation of a people's belief in their capacities, themselves, their freedom, and their self-determination, distancing them from local realities.

The perverted logic of not privileging and respecting interconnections attacks the oppressed people's past, distorting, disfiguring, and destroying their culture and language, depriving their national security of development, and depriving their development of human rights. Trust and ethics are both fundamental for developing civilizations; both are missing in this hegemonistic weapon wielded by dominant powers to annihilate societies' self-belief, subjugate their identities, and promote a globalized sense of selfhood. Northern aid generosity is tied to insensitivity to Others' needs and failure to learn from them..

The Northern cultural-civilizational project fails not only to understand the First World natives' experiences and complexities under globalization, their past conditions, and disconnecting their civilization from their own reality, but it also forces them to identify with things removed from themselves. Such distorted reading of history, which suppresses civilizations that had attained great heights, led natives to view their past as a wasteland of non-achievement. To rediscover the richness and vibrancy of a new transformative civilizing project as opposed to a cultural-civilizing imperialism project challenges this view of the

First World natives as a “wasteland of non-achievement” and upend the subordination of language to the genocide of the civilizing imperial project. Modern disinterest in and devaluation of natives, and these subversive policies of assimilation support our argument that the North is a major contributor to the wasteland of non-achievement and institutionalized cultural-civilizational imperialism. This issue is not a question of ‘colonizing history and language,’ ‘doubling aid,’ or ‘geopolitical policy;’ it is about creating a moral imperative for restorative policy space, with a range of policy alternatives, prioritizing understanding local realities and diverse ways of viewing civilization. Recognition of the truth compels all of us to cease to celebrate successful recolonization and the morally reprehensible partnerships that currently exist.

4. The Underbelly of Colonialism/ Coloniality in Development

Not much has changed since the end of colonization, even in the post-Cold War era. Global futures remain sensitive to policy advice that subverts shared rights to the “brighter sides” of development. The current vision of the neoliberal project of globalization not only monopolize development but also forces people to identify with behaviors far removed from them, inadvertently accelerating the loss of hope within civilizations that have previously served them well. The dominating power of deculturization, false claims of being the ‘storehouse of knowledge,’ and the centrality of geostrategic interests and geopolitical factors—usually extraneous motivations—reveal why native peoples no longer believe in their languages, in their capacities, and in themselves for development solutions. Joseph Stiglitz, in *Towards a New Paradigm for Development: Strategies, Policies, and Processes* (2001), wrote that globalization has failed development, as development is grounded in moral diplomacy, not ethics, to challenge the civil injustices and cultural violence of globalization. The alternative is to force policymakers to respond to the denial of the right to development by unsustainable disruption and exploitation. Numerous countries’ experiences, including African nations, confirm this (Roodman 2004). Inaction to this coloniality of development is not an option.

Colonialism and Coloniality in Development

Exploitative and exclusive globalization results from hegemonic neoliberal intervention, creating dependency on imperialistic world powers, which grasp economic control over other nations. These powers corroborate with the international community’s unwillingness to address the exclusion of Others from global opportunities, or central decision-making systems. Creative exclusion is what neoliberal development has meant, and will continue to mean, if not rethought. Alternatively, inclusive development, with a ‘human face,’ envisions a ‘world community,’ wherein nation-states’ sovereignty is valorized. We have instead observed cultural development and civilizations subordinated through coloniality and colonialist development. Such dominant colonial and capitalist forces exert power in a ‘downward’ direction, dismantling control over agential rights. But the inevitable outcome is native peoples assuming command over their own capacities, and embracing non-paternalistic frameworks that do not waste, marginalize, and subjugate people, and

which define what it means to be civilized. To achieve this, we must address the specific, underlying intent of neoliberal policies in direct conflict with both self-recreation and ideological changes in thinking, which are shifting nations away from the untenable belief in the supremacy of neoliberalism as the only applicable framework for development.

In centering this paper on paternalism and asymmetrical power relations—rather than the presumed self-imposition of colonialism—we rationally conclude that the modern system of education and development's decentering of people and denial of human rights are the heart of the problems and limitations of singularity in development and unsustainable totalizing epistemological framework. This is the reason cultural sophistication and global North civilizational narrative that exhibit prejudices and domination inhibit the struggle to overturn colonial structures rendering other ways of being and knowing invisible to deny self-identification. The failure of the international community and the unwillingness to share economic or power advantages, insufficient for dialogue subordinate home-grown economic/political reforms in this struggle for transformation and self-determination. Obviously, if the goal is to unveil the world or delink the world from the interconnectedness and inter-civilizational contacts of domination and exploitation, pragmatism suggests repudiating and decentering current knowledge system and power structure. Continuous systematic attacks on knowledge fail to shift the geography of knowledge and have failed to move beyond commodification of education (see Maldonado-Torres 2007:11-15). Present underdevelopment is not the fault of humanity—particularly not the African continent, which previously maintained sustainable ways of life that are now considered uncivilized; Africa is not concomitant to the consumerization of social actors' ongoing colonization.

The first step towards decolonization is enabling equal opportunities for First World natives to find their solutions—as expressed in ICCPR (1976) and ICESCR (1966). Education as conceptualized by human capital theory as an economic investment blocks out self-recreation and unlinks knowledge systems from local civilizational ethos. Any systemic effort to attain education's non-economic roles or to recenter cultures necessitates questioning the legitimacy of the cultural-epistemic hegemony and the injustices of the fast-growing market reform policy. With the impact of globalization, education reform policy cannot be free, nor can it develop the productive forces, and improve the oppressed world's comprehensive strength. In this sense, the hidden guidance of this proactive action that misses holistic education prevents people from cultural, social, and non-material aspects of life.

The Global North-South model, which masks the predatory relationship by which the Center develops at the expense of the periphery, suggests that progressive underdevelopment is not the result of self-imposed colonialism, but results from processes that do not necessarily liberate when reproduced on a global scale. Andre Gunder Frank (1966) argues that nation-states have failed to develop, not because of 'internal barriers to development' as neoliberals have argued, but because the powerful and developed North has systematically exploited the South's resources while marginalizing them for its benefit. According to Frank, exploitation drives the North's vested interest in keeping peripheral countries in a state of underdevelopment, allowing developed countries to benefit from their

economic marginalization. To stop the North's prevention of development, we must reclaim our Indigenous voices, reestablish power over our circumstances of underdevelopment, decontrol knowledge unthreatening to Northern prosperity, and critically, participate in the international economic system, which determines how we develop and how we fall.

For his part, Frank, in an article entitled "The Development of Underdevelopment," declares that the colonized live in a coloniality that has remade their history and pushed them to the absolute brink. Underdevelopment is not due to the survival of archaic institutions, or capital shortage in regions isolated from the stream of world history. On the contrary, underdevelopment was and is caused by the same historical process that generated economic development: the development of capitalism itself (1966:18-22). Frank views underdevelopment as a dynamic unity differentiated in terms of power, the search for expandable markets, and control over national resources. He argues that unequal development, or the 'development of underdevelopment,' is a product of decades of capitalism, inflicting its illness on the periphery, forcing them to face the 'darker side' of development through assimilative colonial policy and paternalistic frameworks.

Recognizing that internal factors are unrelated to underdevelopment and critical of what we see as continuing colonization, we suggest destroying false colonial charity and rejecting the extreme, false narratives of neoliberalism, with its triumphalist view of development under its agenda. We therefore propose a new praxis, based on "inclusive and progressive dialogue that respects the Other and cherishes common ground, which turns people from subjected human beings into liberated human beings" (Freire 1970). This decolonization project stems from the centrality of culture in development and the truth of the injustices of colonization and aims to liberate people from the brutality of capitalism, which marginalizes people and emphasizes mainstream development ideology. Likewise, development frameworks must explicitly recognize these injustices and stipulate specific transformative approaches to decoloniality, incorporating them into dynamic and creative national goals.

Recreating Framework(s) for Creative Coloniality

A creative framework for liberation, human security, or developmental freedom requires moving away from single initiatives that diminish ethics and culture as the starting point for development. The unfinished civilization mission project requires the inclusion of previously-ignored valued states of living and addressing false assumptions of global policy agendas. Andreotti and De Souza (2008), in *Learning to Read the World Through Other Eyes*, prove particularly significant for our position. Their argument similarly describes how discriminatory practices and unjust distributions of power impede development. The right to self-determination is rooted in people being central to development; normalizing human rights in development is crucial. Other post-development thinkers, including Claude Ake (1979), have alluded that "development was never really on the agenda in the first place, as such static and mechanistic cultural logic approaches see the Other as barbaric and knowing nothing and awaiting a deposit of ideas." Much like dependency theorists, noting that colonization remains with us, Ake and others argue that resource-rich but economically

poor countries are exploited by more powerful countries through trade imbalances and the extraction of natural resources. The Global North, fearing that developing countries will someday modernize and threaten their dominance, have denied the right to development as a pathway for self-determination. To prevent this, scientific idiocy and thingifying systems have fostered insecurity, stripped beneficiaries of their humanity, and asserted total mental control over natives' right to self-determination. As such, ethical development requires continuous dialogue at each stage of relations, fostering cultural resistance within societies, and commitment to the cause of liberation.

Optimized dialogue and similar initiatives accelerate self-creation for First World natives, including social, cultural, and economic development. When development is no longer linked to localized 'best practices' and ethics, it instead contributes to the domination, oppression, and control of cultural-civilizational imperialism. Such economic and political imperialism remains an obstacle against meaningful dialogue and the freedom of a world of equality. Decoloniality, and the devolution of power, promote trust and guide the establishment of civilization in development.

Superior Civilization Claim in Development

Colonialism's claim to possess a superior civilization is, inherently, a declaration of war over epistemic control and resource exploitation. Colonialists and capitalists claim advanced qualities of civilization and knowledge resulting from constituents whose realities are progressive in their economic, social, cultural, and political modernity. Their epistemic and civil systems, which assign superiority to scientific fantasies, result from the inequitable global economic system and inequities in development. But their global partnerships discourage progressive social transformation; their current challenge is the integration of diverse cultures to create a 'world community' rooted in self-reflection, and with an internalized sense of equal opportunity for all. Such a world community declares that decolonization is the claim of Indigeneity, the recourse of agency, and resistance against subjection; it constitutes self-defense against the war that is colonization. The failure of powerful nations to foster self-determination in developing nations is the basis for their failure to provide adequate international development practices and eliminate colonialism. These pivotal decisions are particularly relevant in a social justice context; the South requires greater freedom.

Such colonialist constriction of knowledge is incongruent with progressive ideals of the right to development. Eradicating developmental impediments has not been a priority for helping developing nations meet their needs and achieve their desired 'modernity.' As noted earlier, solving our varied global challenges requires more diverse cultural options—historical over ahistorical—as it is now apparent that doctrines of secular salvation are less preferable than the protection of human rights, which are most vital for theorizing self-determination. Deskillling knowledge and transforming minds that have been previously denied recreation via historical civilization and destroyed culture, calls for dialogue that assures the continuity of cultural history in development. This is beyond the reach of neoliberalism, which decenters development's political nature, denigrates cultural values,

and mitigates self-modernization. Rather, such dialogue is motivated by the mutually respectful doctrine of human rights, which offers critical considerations against invasive policies for the right to self-determination.

Likewise, William Easterly (2006) writes that, despite all the aid given to the Third World, “superior civilization fallacious concoction and assimilation that constrain examination of the complexity of issues related to development create the problem we face”: little actual development (see Walter Rodney's *How Europe Under-Developed Africa*, 1972). He asserts that the Other possesses the capacity to internalize alternative development paths; thus, “another world is possible,” while “another end of the world” is also possible. Such an end is preventable only by changing mindsets, depoliticizing decolonization, and embracing universalistic ethics by becoming sensitive to diverse ways of learning the world. Oversimplification of historical, cultural, and political institutions “cannibalize state institutions on which any country must depend.” On the other hand, tying transformational struggles to local cultures and histories—or the pathway to civilizational freedom—embodies “self-reflection and revitalization” of values, allowing local knowledge to consolidate culture in development. Thus, overcoming the irresponsible, irrational, and irreparably flawed existing system requires both courage to restore the humanity of everyone involved, and the political inclination to struggle for justice, while still questioning our complicity through introspection.

We are not suggesting “throwing the baby out with the bathwater;” we are only advocating for a “just and ethically rational” transition. Supplanting colonialist interpretive control necessitates overturning colonialist structures. Incorporating a range of voices to represent previously disregarded viewpoints, perspectives, and canons—sidelined by globalization—depends on interrupters of development sacrificing the tainted emotional gratifications they enjoy. These gratifications stem from the toxic relationships that typify colonization and education aid, which counter “home-grown Indigenous perspectives steeped in local culture, histories, and knowledge.” “Cultural-civilizational and epistemic imperialism” has been replaced by “deculturalization.” Appearing to generously narrow the gap of power between modern nations and those they are supposed to civilize, the Global North has instead perfected ethnocide—attacking social, cultural, and political institutions to promote geostrategic interests. With self-development as the mission, our current struggle against five centuries of colonialist traditions and universal solutions is not about making them more oppressed-friendly; rather, we address the absurdity of ignoring human rights, global justice, and the twenty-first century’s moral issue—decolonization.

Lacking a sense of moral responsibility for others, interrupters’ denial of truth perpetuates a constriction of development that is incongruent with the ethics and standards of several United Nations Declarations. Nation-states should not reject development in the broader sense that we have advocated. Rather, nation-states should reject the expansion of the culture of death, irreversible destruction, unrelenting “development,” and international aid that drives our unyielding voices for justice. These aspects of the progressive realization of the right to development, as a means for eradicating global ethnocidal imperialism, are precisely the lessons we must draw for future developmental policy.

5. Missing Elements in Framework(S) of the Right to Development Culture in Development and Ethics in Neoliberalism

The politics of development—neoliberal entrapment of culture and ethics, and genocide suffered by the South—tell the truth: they reject the benign, capitalistic narratives that have dominated humanity's history, driven by neoliberal globalization. The pursuit of such truth—constituting the right to development—considers the need for full respect for individuals' human rights, as well as the duty to promote appropriate cultural, social, economic, and political standards for development. This includes listening to the voice of the Other.

By purveying the falsehood that alternative epistemologies are not possible, neoliberalism shuts down alternative world realities, including the possibility of a just and equitable world where people fulfill their potential and contribute to the economic, cultural, and social transformation of their society. Indeed, such solutions may not stem from the 'scientific' demand for replicability; the surest path to ethics or culture is the right to opacity. These dynamic manifests itself in the international development community's educational policies, and neoliberal capitalism's assumed right to dismiss opacity in people, and their cultures, and in narratives that respect cultural opacity, and accept the unknowable Other as valid. Realizing this progressive, collective ideological initiative, tantamount to human dignity and freedom, requires stakeholders to reject a 'civilization project' that relegates Others to the level of 'savages,' or beneficiaries to an almost subhuman status.

This need for policy rooted in unacceptable realities is not devoid of contradiction. To reject developmental degradation, as organized around development trap models driven by globalization, is to understand colonization. Mohammad Bedjaoui suggests that these unacceptable realities, and the associated missing normative elements in the civilization project itself, are elements of the problem. They are considered 'the Alpha and Omega' for fulfilling the right to development, among other rights, as described by the Vienna Declaration, which affirms such rights as universal and inalienable, and integral to human rights. From this perspective, we consider development as 'inclusive' only when it reduces singularities and disrupts the reductive classification of the Other—classification by imposing foreign knowledge systems and quality of life, which vary often and significantly from those of recipients. There is nothing new here; the global civilization project, instead of offering inclusive development, has strongly contributed to the subjugation and dehumanization of locals.

The popular notion is that simply retooling aid practice, or educating donors on how their misguided current approach impacts how they embrace pluralistic values, will alienate cultural insensitivity, shifting globalization's moral obligation away from promoting the geopolitics of emptying the mind. But in our view, regardless of any 'positives' of globalization—by pressuring First World natives into cultural fakery via disempowerment and false knowledge—there remains the narrowness of current development discourse (see the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness). While aid and other developmental resources have increased, the rule of engagement remains the humanitarian and imperialist North dominating human endeavors, defining geography and inhabitants beyond their nations'

borders, and spreading their dreams around the globe. Colonial systems of political unfreedom and exploitation remain the core of the civilizing project. This is the human cost of human rights entrapments, denied self-determination, and neglect of ethics in the civilizing project. Capitalism, a force of control that prides itself on being the epitome of freedom and democracy, is not the solution for the development of the South. It lacks restorative justice; filled with significant systemic harms that directly shape our present, it can only offer re-colonization and re-enslavement. But such is the nature of imperialism. Conquering both colonization and the ideologies underlying the failure of civilizational projects, systematically and strategically, to recognize the challenges of addressing imperialism with homegrown approaches, requires giving voice to those often ignored by interrupters of development. Platforming these voices leads to decolonizing self-imposed practices of colonization in the making of 'the South.'

Only through cultural development exclusion can the North enjoy all the advantages of the future that it presently enjoys in the status quo. Merely convincing it about what its privilege costs the Other will not lead it to change. It must also undergo a cultural sea change—emotionally, ethically, and even spiritually. A literal example of such a 'sea change' is the life of 18th-century clergyman, and author of the much-beloved hymn *Amazing Grace*, Reverend John Newton. Newton was, before his conversion in the face of a dangerous storm, the captain of a slave-trading ship. His life was spared by the storm; after that, his entire orientation toward slavery changed, and he became a clergyman and an abolitionist. Likewise, rational argumentation may not be enough for those who benefit from colonialism. It will take a change of heart, which is why we also argue for therapeutic modalities, such as rigorously introspective self-examination. Social philosopher Brian Fay (1986) argued the same point decades ago; we are assuming his legacy and his vision in this connection and context.

We describe culture in development as 'irreducible' pluralities in every aspect of ethics of opacity, a commitment to opposition to human rights entrapments, and rejection of ethical insensitivity, as defined by several Articles of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which asserts people's rights to culture in development without dominating interference (Article 11), and to their own political, economic, and social systems (Article 20). Making space for ethics and developing the world means righting injustices against humanity by heeding the previously unheard voices of the marginalized Indigenous population. This begins with meaningful dialogue and includes indigeneity in development. Regardless of motivations or ethical obligations, what we owe each other is a humanity grounded in the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, which strongly supports reciprocity, and recognizes decoloniality beyond neoliberalism.

In our shared struggle for development, when capitalism threatens our ways of being, what matters most is not a given set of relationships, but the inclusivity of the relationships formed—unwrapping the minds of First World natives from global narratives, as well as an abstract interest in the struggle against existing structures of power. Coloniality of knowledge, or global partnerships that fail to adapt foreign knowledge to local contexts—instead, reducing the Other to subhuman status—lead to the objectification of the Other and the commodification of education (see Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2013). Anchoring local

culture in education is imperative for fostering local ownership, and sustainability in a national capacity. The import of these differences, embedded in the 'old development trap model,' widely criticized for trapping normative contents of development, is the argument we make in this paper. For more on this argument, see UNCTAD (2006).

UNCTAD highlights that starving or entrapping a culture is to starve and kill peaceful coexistence in development. We must promote contextual knowledge and account for social and cultural complexities in development. The North's stealing of human rights, and its blind, self-serving interests, explain why, decades after the end of colonialization, exploitation and dehumanization persist, silencing culture and freedom that tie individuals to society, regardless of their needs and differences. For more than five decades, annihilation of society and theft of history have been the norm. Today, people need to secure their freedom by overturning institutions that enable the systemic exploitation of nations and resources. For more on overturning institutions of colonialism, see UNCTAD (2006). The next section explains relevant normative contents of globalization, highlighting its limitations, to provide a point of departure for our subsequent analysis.

Globalization and Development Right of the Other

Under globalization, the Global South is the Other, as it does not conform to constructs of development deemed 'superior' to any other framework. Mainstream thinking, which universalizes developmental thinking and its irrationality, depends on a singular economic vision, forcing participants into capitalism-driven development as subjected members of the world community. Such dependence not only undercuts the dominance of Northern knowledge, but it also challenges the North's oversimplified relations between them and the Other.

Like its colonial predecessors, globalization is a form of economic neo-conservatism. It valorizes 'institutions' through capitalist liberalization, under which all societies must subject themselves—just as Bretton Woods Institutions imposed Structural Adjustment Programs (SAP) but repackaged for the pervasive rhetoric of the global market. These new markets did not promote development with the same confidence as the 1960s reforms. Developmental optimism has been replaced with strategies unsatisfied with holding people in their grip and emptying brains of all form and content; rather, they turn to the past of the oppressed people, and distort, disfigure, and destroy it (Fanon 1961). They distort colonizers' ideologies under the guise of innovative and equitable self-creation. The resulting political divide is strong; the lack of dialogue between powerful and poor countries, described as an impasse, results from dominative and exploitative coloniality. Globalization reinforces the existing order, which contradicts developmental goals valued by First World natives: control over their national resources, and the obliteration of imperialist education and hegemonic structural projects. Winning this battle over ways of being and distributive justice requires expanding the mind to envision new decolonization and achieving the right to self-determination.

Geo-JaJa and Mangum (2001), Geo-JaJa and Zajda (2005), and other native thinkers, such as Paulo Freire, in their analysis of globalization's colonial institutions in development, emphasize the importance of local culture and knowledge. They argue that globalization attributes the right to development only to neoliberal societies deeply rooted in colonialism/capitalism. Not only should such development be rejected, but significant restructuring is imperative: constructing a new global order via a redistribution of power, guided by compassionate ethics and equality for all people, not just citizens of the North. Likewise, eradicating the exploitative relationship between North and South, and overturning institutions that support the global exploitation of people and resources, is imperative to restore denied culture, for mutual liberation, political security, and enjoyment of self-development. Such rejection of globalism is born from its Northern imperialism and its political and economic order, which promotes disguised non-development, sidelines the interests of the Global South, and perpetuates global underdevelopment.

Recognizing the brutal immorality underpinning the 1884 Berlin conference over the European colonization of Africa, Mamdani (2013) claims that the international struggle over Africa is the dialectical colonial order of things. This de-Africanization, manifesting through territoriality and economic policies, did not serve the colonized well. European assumptions of capitalism homogenized diverse African cultures, centered dominant imperialism over ethical accountability, and left lived experiences as the unquestionable truth. Liberating natives from cultural imperialism suggests a decolonization rooted in human rights, encompassing the rights to self-development and self-determination. We must realign with historical values that sustained our communities before invasion and colonization, return to and advance our own identities, and assert control over natural resources, shaped through human rights. Self-determination demands having a voice in the utilization of national resources, and respect for and implementation of the developmental voice of First World natives.

In *Decolonizing the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature*, Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o argues that:

Colonialism detonated a "cultural bomb" that almost annihilated people's belief in their language, heritage, and environment and made them regard their cultural background as "a wasteland of non-achievement" that had to be left behind as quickly as possible [Ngugi 1986:6-12]

The significance of human rights also resonated with Stephen Mark (2004), Mignolo (2007), and Rahnema and Bawtree (1997), who explain that the realization of all human rights in development is decoloniality, including exercising the inalienable right to ways of being, and opposition to all forms of institutionalized oppression. This must begin with acts of reparative, redistributive, and ethical social justice, ensuring full native sovereignty over natural resources, in contrast to the current developmental yoke of having economies locked behind relationships of exploitation, currently manifested through assumed epistemic and cultural superiority. Intellectuals contend that developmental human rights declare not only an urgent call for justice, but also demand overdue protection from perverse colonial

institutions, and from ferocious imperialist efforts to restore colonialism through invisible matrices of power that weaken institutions of the resource-rich but economically poor (see Escobar 2012; Stiglitz 2005; Veltmeyer & Petras 2005; UNCTAD 2006). At the end of the Cold War, new institutionalized exploiters, such as NGOs, exacerbated the situation; they disbursed aid with little or no oversight from recipients. As evidenced by the literature, despite commitment to participation and bottom-up approaches, the global focus is still on upward accountability, as enforced by donor countries, rigid frameworks, and 'one-size-fits-all' approaches, each remarkably unimpactful for addressing local poverties of voice and assets, and tackling other complexities of globalization, including exploitation.

President George W. Bush best articulates the demands of equitable development, which requires both downward accountability and the cooperation of the international aid community, refraining from any conduct that mitigates or bottlenecks the exercise of the right to self-development:

Developed nations have a duty not only to share our wealth but also to encourage sources that produce wealth: economic freedom, political liberty, the rule of law, and human rights We fight against poverty because opportunity is a fundamental right to human dignity. We fight against poverty because faith requires it, and conscience demands it. ... I'm here today to call for a new compact for development defined by greater accountability for rich and poor nations alike (March 22, 2002).

This powerful rhetoric, which offers hope to disenfranchised people at the margins of globalization—hope for the struggle against globalization—also places greater weight on commitment to bottom-up approaches, anchored in trust, and the development of local decision-making and knowledge systems. Without this greater commitment, such hopes are only dashed hopes, and the right to development anywhere will remain just a dream.

Most would agree that pathways toward development, for the sake of global justice, should do more than merely reaffirm the right to development or the fruit of development, which has undergone ideological warfare (Fanon, 1961; Ngugi 1986:6-12; Maldonado-Torres 2007; Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2012). Positive change remains elusive, as we continue to conduct development in tandem with institutions of colonialism and the culture of imperialism. Even the UNDP argued that development has broken down under globalization, and abysmally failed "emancipatory development," conveying instead the idea of comprehensive rights to partnership (2001:10). This is not to say that every neoliberal reform policy and intervention has failed. But globalization is all about de-historicizing, depoliticizing, and deculturizing development. Its claim of superiority, crucial to the domination of the mental universe of the Other, neglects to promote the voices of the poor, marginalized, and powerless and fails to ensure that people impacted by coloniality are heard and understood. Ake (1979), Fanon (1961), and Mamdani (2013) argue that privileged power and universalism disrupt the assertion of UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan, who asserted that:

We will not enjoy development without security, we will not enjoy security without development, and we will not enjoy either without respect for human rights (Report of the

Secretary-General, "In Larger Freedom: Towards Development, Security and Human Rights for All," 2005).

Human rights are at the heart of human existence and development. We direct our critiques at globalization's predatory theft of the South's right to self-determination, as globalization imposes its consumerist culture on the entire world. In a recent report, the UNCTAD concluded that, despite recognizing neoliberalism's failings and the genitive impact of SAP on African countries, there have been no attempts to redress imbalances in developmental capacities or to help less powerful nations restructure and adjust capacities that have kept development low. These lacks suggest that the global fight against poverty, and the international human rights goals to improve the well-being of all, have failed reparative justice (UNCTAD, 2002); we attribute this to a lack of recognition of reality, denial of developmental voices, and a lack of social justice and ethics in development.

Overall, the global civilization project, centered on geopolitical interests and the expansion of capitalism, reflects the constraints and contradictions inherent in globalized neoliberal practices, which anesthetize people to a culture of consumerism and adjust policies towards prepackaged development. This anesthetization, which culminates in the shackles of globalization, must be dismantled, and local knowledge production must be repositioned and aligned with unencumbered moral agency (see Mignolo 2007; Maldonado-Torres 2007; both cited in Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2012).

Like its UNDP counterpart, UNCTAD contends that:

Two-and-a-half decades of standardized packages of "stabilization, liberalization, and privatization," rather than choosing the right kind of approach, has simply failed to materialize across most of the continent. ... (UNCTAD, 2006).

Little trust is given to these agencies in aid conditionalities—including those aiming to get institutions right. Just as in the upward accountability approach, the World Bank concluded a failure rate of over 80 percent in African aid. In most cases, aid has been counterproductive (UNCTAD 2002; Geo-JaJa and Mangum 2001). Despite this 'darker side' of the new imperialist development push, there is significant potential for neoliberal capitalism to assist, predicated on reciprocity, or cross-cultural practices (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2012): shifting away from irrational "one-size-fits-all" approaches, toward a rational decolonization of development (Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2013; Maldonado-Torres 2007). These scholars noted that the existing system only represses and punishes the South, while at the same time advantaging the North. Inverting Walter Mignolo, Mamdani (2019) argues that development, entangled with colonialism, privileges the prerogatives, economic infrastructures, and geopolitical interests of the North, which uses development aid to further its hegemony. The current Global North Code of Practice ensures that they remain part of the problem, not part of the solution to promote global development.

To understand the relevance of these definitive arguments beyond their local specificity, understanding decolonization is imperative. Decolonization sets out to change the order of the world by attacking power imbalances and creating essential external conditions, turning modalities inside-out, allowing greater space for policy, and integrating the ethics, lives, and consciousness of the South. This reengineering process fundamentally transforms First World natives, formerly crushed into a subhuman status, into a new generation of humanity, with a new language and new identity. Self-development and pluralist repackaging create room for valued developmental voices by overturning institutions of colonialism harmful to them.

Globalization's greatest challenge is its failure to recreate local reality and national loyalty and to replace harmful institutions with systems that respect the creation of desired lives, according to local realities. As Mamdani (1998) and others have noted, under modern normative factors and welfare capitalism's conceptualization of development, reimagining the past and shaping the future of the Global South is only achievable through the reconstruction of historical, civilizational, and political rights perspectives (Mignolo 2007; Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2013a, 2013b; and Maldonado-Torres 2011). These limiting factors, in their gross disregard of ethics and receptive generosity, decenter the centrality of people in development. People offer human subjectivity, as featured in human rights frameworks including, *inter alia*, the UN Declarations cited in this paper. As others have argued, we contend that the need to promote human rights is particularly dire, given these widespread deprivations of human rights, the neglect of equitable voices in international decisions and policies, and consequent impediments to equitable development. It is unlikely that colonialist neoliberalism will rebalance capitalism, or redress power imbalances in development, in support of localized development.

6. Conclusion and Lessons Learned

As indicated earlier, nothing has changed for First World natives. Current reforms and interventions bear the imprint of colonialist economic adventurism. Under this new colonialism, the Global North imposes horrendous injustices on the South, as it perpetuates policies against self-determination. It claims the right to confiscation and domination in development, just as colonialists have exploited, subjugated, and annihilated people. We contend that these imperial elements in international relations dominate the mental universe of the South, as its internalized image of the North adopts a false generosity, nourished by an unjust social order maintained to justify its oversimplification of reality and inhumanity.

We cannot expect positive development from politicized aid programs that fail to respect the views of the Other. The North believes it must be the executor of social transformation programs, good intentions notwithstanding. Thus, 'development' continues to mean underdevelopment in the colonized heart and mind of the Other. Given these limitations of existing neoliberal false generosity, and drawing on norms established in noted UN Declarations, we require new global relationships, founded on this fight against neoliberal coloniality—which, with its covert objective of stealing the world. is the source of current problems in the liberation struggle. We must fight to carry the indigeneity flag, secure our own emancipation, and celebrate diversity unmarred by "cultural bombs,"

centered in sovereignty and freedom for all. As neoliberalism disrupts reciprocity, ignores ethics, and remains insensitive to the Other, we challenge its solutions via aid generosity, predicated on development that has been repackaged as poison (Illich 2006; Easterlin 1981; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2012).

Following Steven Marks (2004), Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2012), and Claude Ake (???), we argue that this politicization of the right to development, and hesitant support for and outright hostility to culture development from the international donor community—particularly Bretton Woods Institutions (BWI) privileging the Global North’s agenda—is antithetical to development consistent with ethics that produce economic and political liberty. Such rhetorical support for agential rights that simultaneously neglects basic precepts of development, and undercuts peoples’ capacity to help themselves, we term ‘development as poison’: developmental entrapment, the inadvertent enemy of both human development and the neoliberal project of globalization (Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2013; Illich 2006; Wu and Geo-JaJa 2016). In our view, culture is a precondition for countries to focus properly on other priorities of economic growth, health, and education for all citizens. However, allowing people full cultural expression is an important development end.

Within the context of self-determination, the United States and other donor countries stress that development results from economic liberties and capitalism, not a claimed right to cultural liberty or right to development—without being excluded from other alternatives that are important to them. Thus, they not only objected to this claim, but they also voted against this broad view of development, which includes cultural liberty and development as freedom, which recognizes that denying these claims can lead to incredibly significant privations at the United Nations. As such, neoliberalism’s negation of local culture and rights to development serves as the litmus test by which we can assess the multiplicity of Global Northern motives. This article provides some historical insights into the transformation of identity; however, it is more of a conceptual analysis of foundational categories of the settler-colonialism paradigm. Our conceptual analysis of colonialism suggests a revised, reality-driven decoloniality that considers the erroneous narrative of modern development and the gamut of reforms embedded in cultural-civil imperialism. The latter claims its triumphalist view of development under its agenda as the only approach to actual generous developmental cooperation.

In closing, avoiding such tragic results of policy requires the deglobalization and debalkanization of global aid generosity, predicated on development repackaged as freedom. More importantly, in their reconstruction of colonial dynamics in development, and addressing the “stubborn issue of inequalities, oppression, false generosity, and exploitation,” the authors recommend dismantling the hegemony of neoliberal globalization and its framing and reconstructing neoliberalism to listen to the Other. Pushing society onto this path of political and developmental freedom requires ethical relations and anticolonial thinking, ensuring self-determination by depoliticizing the right to development. Recognizing that brutal colonialism remains a reality today, the first major step towards decolonization is decentering the enslavement of the mind, which in earlier eras created possibilities for new worlds.

The central argument in favor of privileging ethics and reparative justice is our need to decolonize thinking by overturning colonial structures, privileging reciprocity and decentering the enslavement of the mind, liberating people from oppression that disconnects them from their roots. Empowering citizens to become more proactive opens their minds to new knowledge, culture, and developmental paths, resulting in a liberated future founded on old cultures and identities. This liberation reinforces Indigenous peoples' social and political order "in which civic rights are the Indigenous people's rights" (Mamdani, 1998:2)—manifesting, yet again, the centrality of culture in development.

In a major way, cultural liberation and development as freedom returns hope—for a 'good life,' or for new humanism, in development. Just as Claude Ake noted, the reality of development extends far beyond the economic; it is multidimensional, extending to the development of voices (agential and political representation), and the current lack of freedom (liberation and sovereignty), as evidenced through limited neoliberal globalization—which, being associated with coloniality, keeps people subjugated and exploited.

To sum up, the paper argues that development aid failed, as development has not always been Global North's objective. Even when it has been successful, it fails to accommodate cultural diversity; too often, its efforts have been guided by international aid stemming from repressive knowledge systems, rather than harnessing creative diversity that dismantles colonial structures and rebalances power for cultural development, which makes all the difference in development. Home-grown solutions call to deepen decolonization and de-imperialization from hegemonic international capitalism, instead foster globalization "with a human face." The need for cultural development in coloniality speaks about integral human development transversalizing the new sign-post in development. In line with post-development scholars, the viable instrument to context universalized modernity - forced assimilation, unequal integration, undermining human rights, destroying culture, and undermining of self-understanding, to enshrine civilizational identity and right to development is dismantling the colonial power matrix (Quijano 2007; Ndlovu-Gatsheni 2013). In the context of education," the potent weapon in the hands of the Global North is to delink "modernity" that fosters violent underbelly of global inequalities and economic imperialism control (Grosfoguel, 2006; Grosfoguel, Maldonado-Torres, 2016; Mignolo, 2009; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2015b; Quijano, 2007). In short the universalized conception of humanity and the restitution of Global North superiority that distorts cultural-historical origins is reasoned why there is no imperialist development without coloniality.

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